

“METHODS OF FAST CALCULATION”

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Relevance of the Project: This research work presents information, data, and calculation results clearly and comprehensively. In addition, some numbers have unique natural properties that make fast calculations possible, and through these properties, they gain educational and even mysterious characteristics.

Goal: To develop the skill of fast calculations that are necessary in daily life and useful in modern society.

Objectives:

- To develop the ability to solve mathematical problems;
- To form knowledge of fast calculation methods;
- To improve basic skills of fast calculation when solving problems;
- To develop practical skills as a factor in personal growth.

Expected Result: Students will learn and use non-standard fast calculation methods, and develop interest in the process.

Mathematics plays an enormous role in human life. Without the ability to count, add, subtract, multiply, and divide correctly, it is impossible to imagine the development of human society. Mathematics reflects life through numbers. It is known that humanity learned to count even before writing was invented. If we can calculate quickly in our mind, why do we need calculators? Many of my classmates get annoyed when they have to multiply without a calculator. Today, calculators are everywhere: on phones, watches, notebooks—anywhere modern designers could fit them. So, the question arises: why should we bother?

My interest in this topic started during math lessons. We study arithmetic, one of the most important sections of mathematics, and our main task is to count quickly and accurately. At first, mathematical dictations took my classmates and me too much time, and when we were in a hurry, we made many mistakes. It became interesting for me to learn simple methods for multiplying, dividing, and exponentiating numbers. When you don't have a calculator, table, or even a pen and paper, oral calculation methods will definitely help.

Fast Multiplication and Division of Natural Numbers

Quick Multiplication by 11

One special method to speed up calculation is multiplication by 11.

Example: Multiply 26 by 11.

Add the digits: $2 + 6 = 8$.

Insert the sum between the original digits: 286.

If the sum of the digits is a two-digit number, the first digit is added to the tens place of the original number. Example:

$75 \times 11 \rightarrow 7 + 5 = 12 \rightarrow$ add 1 to 7 $\rightarrow 8$, insert 2 $\rightarrow 825$

More examples:

- $54 \times 11 = 594$
- $124 \times 11 = 1364$
- $58 \times 11 = 638$
- $67 \times 11 = 737$

General rule:

$35 \times 11 = 3(3+5)5 = 385$

$73 \times 11 = 7(7+3)3 = 803$

Quick Multiplication of Numbers Ending in 1

Example:

81×31

$8 \times 3 = 24$ (hundreds)

$8 + 3 = 11$ (tens)

$1 \times 1 = 1$ (units)

Result: 2511

Quick Division by 5, 25, and 125

To divide by these numbers, multiply by 2, 4, or 8 respectively, then divide by 10, 100, or 1000.

Examples:

$220 \div 5 = (220 \times 2) \div 10 = 44$

$1300 \div 25 = (1300 \times 4) \div 100 = 52$

$9250 \div 125 = (9250 \times 8) \div 1000 = 74$

5, 25, 125 сандарына шапшаң бөлу әдісі

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• $9250:125=(9250\times 8):1000=74$

Finger Method for Multiplying by 9

This ancient method is especially useful for beginners who struggle with multiplication. Number the fingers from left to right.

To multiply a number by 9, bend the finger corresponding to the number.

Example: $4 \times 9 \rightarrow$ bend the 4th finger.

3 fingers remain to the left (tens = 30), 6 to the right (units = 6).

Answer: 36

This method works only for multiplying by 9.

Conclusion: Mathematics is essential in everyday life. However, the growing use of computers and calculators has slowed students' development of fast mental calculation and logical thinking skills. Therefore, each student should practice oral exercises regularly to train their mind. While preparing this research project, I explored several fast calculation methods and proved their effectiveness through solving various problems. I discovered that different types of problems are connected and that learning fast calculation techniques helps deepen mathematical understanding.

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